

An Analysis of the Spatial Effects in Severe Transients for a Numerical Benchmark Representative of the CABRI Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Safety analysis usually rely on system codes with embedded dimensionless point kinetics models to evaluate margins to critical phenomena during transients. In this work, a cell-core approach using Condor-CITVAP and a dynamic Monte Carlo approach using Serpent are considered to reproduce a numerical-benchmark problem for a severe transient with adiabatic feedback, representative of the well-known CABRI reactor. Being both approaches capable to capture the spatial details, an investigation of the effect on key parameters due to different levels of discretization in the feedback representation is developed. For both approaches, which are inherent independent in terms of methods, approximations and models, the same tendency was observed. That is, a poor spatial representation of the adiabatic feedback leads to a noticeable underestimation of the negative feedback. Consequently, the importance of these sophisticated approaches which are capable to capture the spatial, temporal and energetic intricacies in realistic transient scenarios is addressed.

Keywords: Cell-core, Spatial Kinetics, transients, dynamic Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Safety analysis usually rely on system codes (e.g. RELAP, TRACE, PARET/ANL) to address that the available margins to the limiting critical phenomena are sufficient for a particular design during transients [1]. These codes were originally developed during the 1960's to serve as fast tools that model small-break loss-of-coolant accidents and evolved to be able to model the span of transients that might occur during the operation of a nuclear reactor with reasonable accuracy. In particular, to capture the evolution of the neutron population during these transients, simplified models that consider a space-independent solution for the problem, i.e., implementations of the Point Kinetics (PK) equations, are embedded as internal modules.

The application of these codes represents a standard approach for safety-related analyses for research reactors [1]. In particular, these are regularly applied to address the safety margins for research reactors even for rapid and severe Reactivity Insertion Accidents (RIA).

Nevertheless, during the last decades, the development of advanced methodologies in reactor physics, combined with the availability of vast computational resources allowed to embark transient problems with a noticeable lower level of approximations in the space, energy and time modelling of the neutronic problem. This is of particular interest when dealing with research reactors, since the reduced dimensions of their cores and the availability of experimental data create a valuable field in which to test and evaluate the accuracy, viability and potential scalability of these advanced methods.

In this work, a numerical benchmark problem that reproduces the main neutronic characteristics of the CABRI reactor is considered, originally developed in the framework of an IAEA Coordinated Research Project [2]. Here, the analysis is aimed to investigate the added value that these advanced methodologies could provide when dealing with rapid and severe transients in compact cores.

In particular, the analysis here is developed using two complete independent methodologies that are able to capture the main phenomenology of transients, reproducing the spatial and time evolution of the neutron field in the reactor core and surroundings. Therefore, a traditional cell-core approach using Condor-CITVAP codes and a dynamic Monte Carlo approach using Serpent code are applied, including

an adiabatic TH feedback in both cases. Being both approaches capable to represent different levels of spatial detail in the TH feedback, the idea is thus to investigate their effect on key parameters to then infer the potential gain and insights of the use of these methodologies in realistic scenarios.

2. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE CABRI-LIKE NUMERICAL BENCHMARK PROBLEM

The numerical benchmark here analyzed represents a problem-solution verification case for an almost purely-neutronic fast and severe transient case, developed in the framework of an IAEA collaborative project [2]. The geometry and materials definition are based on the well-known CABRI reactor, which is a pool-type research reactor located at Cadarache, operated by CEA [3]. It has a maximum operating power of 25 MW in steady-state operation, but was designed to investigate fast transients in geometries compatible with pressurized water reactors. It features a compact core (~65 cm square and ~80 cm active length), reflected by graphite, with a square lattice fuel rod configuration composed of ~1488 stainless steel clad UO₂ rods (enriched to ~6 %wgt). These fuel rods are combined with structural and poisoned ones to form 40 Fuel Assemblies (FA). The core reactivity is mainly controlled by 6 Control Rods (CR), composed of groups of 23 hafnium rods that can be axially inserted into the core. A peculiarity of its design is a dedicated fast reactivity injection system, composed of a series of tubes placed in specific fuel assemblies in the core, which are filled by ³He (a strong neutron absorber) and are connected to a closed system. These can be suddenly depressurized to initiate transients of diverse severity, where the core's inherent negative feedbacks are responsible for the reactivity counterbalance. Besides, it includes a central experimental loop and two irradiation channels that are also placed in core for specific experiments involving transients.

A numerical benchmark for this CABRI reactor was developed in [2], basically applying some geometrical and material simplifications that preserve its main neutronic characteristics. Besides, real depressurization curves for ³He transient rods are also provided for scenarios that produce real transients of increasing severity, setting a 0.15 s time scope for the analysis.

This work deals with a specific transient from [2] identified as "HIGH", i.e., a prompt-supercritical case with an initial power of 100 kW. This scenario is compatible with the most demanding one reported [3], which reaches a power peak of ~20 GW after the depressurization from ~11.5 bar in ³He rods.

Besides, to represent the reactivity feedbacks that counterbalances the introduced reactivity (from the ³He depressurization), this numerical benchmark proposes a simplified adiabatic representation of the heat transfer problem. Thus, the power for each portion of the FA is used to calculate the increase on the fuel temperature (T_{fuel}), considering that all additional heat is directly translated into the fuel:

$$T_{fuelX}^i = T_{fuelX}^{i-1} + \frac{Q_{fuelX}^{i-1} - Q_{fuelX}^{i=0}}{m_{fuelX} cp} \quad (1)$$

where T_{fuel} is the fuel temperature, fuelX identifies the portion of the FA to consider, i represents the time step, m is the UO₂ mass (in kg) of the portion, cp is set to 300 J/kgK and Q identifies the energy deposited in the portion of the FA in the time step i.

3. CONSIDERED APPROACHES AND MODELS DEVELOPED

As aforementioned, the main object of this work is to investigate the impact of the spatial representation of the neutronic problem when dealing with fast and severe transients in realistic compact core configurations. For such purpose, completely independent methodologies are here applied, which consider alternative models, approximations and methodologies to solve the proposed problem.

3.1. Dynamic Monte Carlo approach using the code Serpent

Serpent v2.2 is a state-of-the-art Monte Carlo (MC) transport code developed by VTT (Finland), extensively verified and validated for criticality, burnup, fixed source and dynamic calculations [4]. In particular, it has the peculiarity of being able to easily handle distributions of TH parameters (e.g.,

temperatures and densities) using superimposed meshes defined separately, which makes it especially suitable for this transient benchmark problem.

Models for the CABRI-like benchmark in [2] were developed including the explicit representation of all components, as shown in Figure 1. Besides, superimposed meshes (IFC, see [4]) per FA were included, with different axial discretization levels. Regarding nuclear data, ENDF/B VII.1 ACE was considered.

The initial configuration of the transient was used to save precursors and live neutron sources. As a rule, criticality calculations were developed considering 3000 cycles with 10^5 particles each, while transient calculations consider time bins of 0.5 ms with 2×10^6 particles on each of them, divided in 500 batches (300 time bins for the 0.15 time scope). The update of the T_{fuel} during these transients is done using Serpent semaphores and a python script, where the data for the superimposed meshes is updated for each time step. The only driver for the transient is thus the change in the ^3He density in the transient rods, which is replicated from the benchmark specifications [2].

a) Serpent model xy cut at core centre, showing the superimposed meshes (IFC) for each FA.

a) Serpent model xz cut in the CR zone, showing the superimposed meshes w/10 axial discretization (IFC).

Figure 1. Serpent v2.2 models for the CABRI-like numerical benchmark using IFC [4].

3.2. Cell-core approach using Condor-CITVAP codes

An alternative cell-core approach was also considered, using the in-house neutronic calculation codes developed by INVAP. These calculation codes are tailored to model research reactor intricacies, where extensive verification and validation efforts for similar configurations can be found in [5], [6] and [7].

For cell-level calculations, the code Condor v2.8.08 is considered. It is a fast-running and versatile tool that can solve 1D and 2D multi-group cell-level problems by means of variations of the collision probabilities integral method [6]. For core level calculations CITVAP v3.9.06 code is used [5]. It is a core-level code that solves the multigroup diffusion equation using finite differences method in 1D, 2D and 3D geometries and includes Spatial Kinetics capabilities [7] to deal with transient problems.

Models for Condor and CITVAP were developed, as show in Figure 2. The Condor 2D cell-level model represented a quarter geometry using a 69-Energy group ENDF/B VII.1 Nuclear Data Library. Further condensation to a 3-group structure (energy group limits 0.625 eV, 0.821 MeV and 10 MeV) was applied for selected portions to obtain a working library for CITVAP core-level calculations. This working library included dependence in T_{fuel} for the fuels and a parameterization in ^3He pressure for the transient rods zone. Then, a 3D quarter core model was developed CITVAP 3D, where the axial representation for the core active zone was discretized in 60 zones. This allowed to easily represent

different TH feedbacks by means of collapsing the axial zones for the T_{fuel} interpolation. Thus, the calculated power was used to update the T_{fuel} , condensing the zones to the selected number of axial representation of the TH feedback.

Figure 2. Cell (Condor) and Core (CITVAP) models for CABRI-like numerical benchmark

3.3. Point Kinetics Model

To complement the analysis, a Point Kinetics (PK) representation of the problem was also included. Here, the aim is to obtain a solution compatible with the one that a system code would produce [1]. Thus, the PK equations with adiabatic feedback were solved using the kinetic parameters, reactivity insertion curves (from ^3He depressurization) and feedback coefficients obtained from Serpent steady-state calculations. This PK model was implemented in OCTAVE [8], using a stiff Ordinary Differential Equation solver (the ode23s, described in [9]), where details are not provided to preserve compactness.

3.4. Spatial discretization of the problem

As aforementioned, diverse representations of the spatial phenomenology were analyzed in this work, preserving the FA representation of the TH feedback, but modifying the axial level of detail to update Tfuel during the transient evolution. Thus, Serpent models were run using a 1, 5 and 10 axial discretization of the TH feedback, just altering the definition of the superimposed meshes. As for Condor-CITVAP, calculations were run using 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 30 and 60 axial zones to apply the Tfuel feedback. Finally, it should be noted that the PK model does not take into account any spatial detail.

4. MAIN RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Impact of the discretization in the total power and Tfuel evolution

The results from Serpent and Condor-CITVAP models for the total power and average Tfuel increase during the transient for different axial discretization at FA are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, where the time scope where the power peak occurs is selected to be plotted. It should be noted that despite having both models an initial near critical configuration, the starting condition for the transients was forced to be critical (by means of adjusting the production and losses balances in the codes). Besides, the initial fuel temperatures and total power were set to 20 °C and 100 kW respectively. Here, the PK results were included in the Serpent plots (in Figure 3) to provide a fair comparison, since the parameters from former steady-state calculations in Serpent are considered in the PK model.

Figure 3. Serpent results using models from Section 3.1 for the CABRI-like benchmark “HIGH” case in [2], for diverse axial discretizations of the TH feedback (by FA). Results from PK models from Section 3.3 are included (using parameters from Serpent steady-state calculations). Serpent results include the reported statistical error from calculations at 1σ. Initial power is 100kW.

Figure 4. Condor-CITVAP results using models from Section 3.2 for the CABRI-like benchmark “HIGH” case in [2] for diverse axial discretizations of the TH feedback (by FA). Initial power is 100kW.

4.2. Impact of the discretization in the maximum Power and Tfuel increase

To complement the results from Figure 3 and Figure 4, the maximum power and the maximum average Tfuel increases for the whole time scope (i.e. 0.15 s) are provided in Table I for the diverse approaches and axial discretization of the TH feedback.

Table I. Summary for the maximum power and average Tfuel increase using different approaches and axial TH feedback discretizations (by FA) for case “HIGH” in CABRI-like benchmark [2]. Initial power is 100kW.

Code / discretization	Serpent ⁺		Condor-CITVAP		PK (using serpent parameters)	
	P _{max} [GW]	ΔT _{ave} [K]	P _{max} [GW]	ΔT _{ave} [K]	P _{max} [GW]	ΔT _{ave} [K]
0 - dimensional					32.5	1502
1 Axial zone	30.3	1478	24.1	1286		
2 Axial zones			21.1	1154		
3 Axial zones			19.1	1059		
5 Axial zones	22.4	1107	18.1	1014		
10 Axial zones	20.9	1068	17.7	996		
30 Axial zones			17.6	991		
60 Axial zones			17.6	991		

⁺ Statistical error in Serpent calculation for the maximum power bins is ~10%.

4.3. Analysis of the main findings

The analysis of the results from Figure 3, Figure 4 and Table I show that, regardless the observed discrepancies, a consistent behavior is reproduced by all approaches, addressing that the underlying physics during the transient were captured. That being said, the potential origin of the spotted differences for the power and the increase of the average Tfuel between approaches and axial discretization are here discussed.

Regarding differences between approaches, the first thing to be noted is that each of the proposed methodologies have a different inherent approximations. For the full-3D MC dynamic approach, the space, energy and time variables of the neutron fields are explicitly considered. For the cell-core approach the spatial and time variables are preserved, but a successive condensation to few-energy groups is applied, thus some spectral detail could be lost. Finally, the PK models have no spatial nor energetic dependence. Thus, these approaches range for lower (i.e. dynamic MC) to a higher (i.e. PK) number of approximations in the representation of this benchmark problem. The obvious trade-off of these is the impact on modelling complexity and computational requirements, where the dynamic MC required $\sim 1 \times 10^5$ CPU mins (@2.4GHz CPU), whereas the cell-core approach required ~ 200 CPU mins in the same CPU and the PK requirement was almost negligible. Probably one of the most interesting findings here is that, in principle, all these were able to reproduce the main aspects of this fast and severe transient (i.e. power peaks magnitude, position in time, main T_{fuel} behavior), which includes a power increase with several orders of magnitude and a noticeable temperature increase. Conversely, if results are in-depth analyzed the discrepancies become clear, where the maximum power and T_{fuel} increase showed differences of 15% for power and 100 K respectively between Serpent and Condor-CITVAP. These differences can be easily attributed to slight differences in the actual ^3He reactivity worth or T_{fuel} reactivity feedback from both approaches. That being said, the differences with PK approach become noticeable higher, even if the parameters from Serpent steady-state are considered and the comparison is made with Serpent's results.

These differences lead to the additional finding of the analysis here proposed, related to the relevance of considering the spatial characteristics of the actual feedback that occurs in the reactor in this fast and severe transient. As seen in Figure 4 a) and b), both the dynamic MC and the cell-core approaches, which are inherently independent, reflect the same behavior with the axial discretization considered to update the T_{fuel} during the transient. That is, the decrease of the discretization increases the calculated maximum power (and ΔT_{fuel}), where after ~ 10 axial zones almost no effect is observed. Conversely, for a single zone discretization, the power peak is observed to be higher, whereas is key to note that if Serpent results are analyzed, the agreement with PK is improved (see Figure 3). The underlying phenomena that explains this behavior can be attributed to actual differences in the resulting reactivity balance for this severe transient due to the spatial effects, namely the over or under representation of the increase of the temperature in zones where the neutron importance is actually higher or lower. Thus, obtaining a better detail in the T_{fuel} representation evolution (such as in Serpent or Condor-CITVAP approaches), the actual reactivity due to negative feedbacks is calculated with higher accuracy, thus affecting the counter-balance of the introduced reactivity by the ^3He depressurization and altering the power evolution. The capability to capture this effect becomes paramount, since, in principle, the importance of is not always easy to identify in advance. Here, it should be noted here that spatially-averaged PK parameters could be considered in PK models to capture such effects, but, again, this is not an information available prior to the analysis (neither the level of spatial discretization required for such average to be accurate). A clear gain of the detailed approaches here is thus that these allow to easily identify the level of detail that should be considered by a simple discretization analysis.

As a corollary, the analysis here developed showed the importance of analyzing the potential spatial effects when dealing with transient scenarios that are not known in advance, specially were these are severe or fast. Here, the analysis was done for a realistic scenario representative of a real operating research reactor as CABRI and noticeable effects were spotted. In particular, departing from traditional (PK) analysis and increasing the level of detail in the problem representation was found to be valuable. Here, in case no spatial detail is considered, the negative reactivity feedback is found to be underestimated, leading to differences up to 40 % in peak power (see results for Condor-CITVAP results, also reflected in increased average T_{fuel}). An interesting additional aspect to remark here is that the Condor-CITVAP approach includes successive condensation in the energy variable (i.e. from 69-groups in cell-level calculations to 3-groups in core-level calculations in CITVAP) whereas the neutron energy is explicitly modelled in Serpent, but the same tendency is observed, thus adding additional insights that indicate that the potential spectral effects are not the main reason for this observed behavior.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Point kinetics models are the common choice to represent the power evolution during transients in system codes used for safety analyses. In this work, a severe and fast transient scenario with an

adiabatic TH feedback is in-depth analyzed, aimed to spot conditions where these PK models approximations could show limitations. This scenario is a problem-solution (numerical) benchmark representative of the well-known CABRI reactor, where fast transients can be triggered by the sudden reactivity insertion by an ad-hoc system, leading to noticeable power and temperature increases.

The analysis here is developed using different methodologies and level of detail in the representation of this problem. Thus, models using a 3D spatial and explicit temporal representation were developed using cell-core (i.e., Condor-CITVAP) and a dynamic MC (i.e., Serpent), which are inherently independent in terms of methods, approximations and models. The analysis was complemented with the comparison with PK models (using parameters from Serpent steady-state calculations), which are compatible with the approach considered by most of the system codes.

This allowed to investigate the effect of different levels of discretization in the TH feedback representation on the evolution of key parameters during this severe transient. It was found that, for both approaches, a poor spatial representation of the adiabatic feedback can easily lead to a noticeable underestimation of the negative feedback and thus an overestimation of maximum power and fuel temperature increases. As a result, counting with these more sophisticated approaches, which are capable to capture the spatial, temporal and energetic intricacies in realistic transient scenarios, was found to be a valuable additional tool for the analysis. This becomes of particular interest when the peculiarities of the scenario or inherent characteristics of the problem are not known in advance.

Encouraged by the results here obtained, further work would try to expand these findings to more complex scenarios or geometrical configurations. Besides, the analysis for spatial and temporal detailed margins to critical phenomena becomes straightforward, since the detailed power evolution is now available. Nevertheless, the validation of these additional observables remains as an open-issue.

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